

CONDUCTIVE POLYANILINE NANOCOMPOSITES: ELECTROCHROMIC BEHAVIOR, ELECTROCHEMICAL ENERGY STORAGE AND GIANT MAGNETORESISTANCE SENSOR

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1 Introduction

Sustainable and renewable energy resources are in increasing demand due to the depletion of fossil fuels and climate change. Therefore, to develop efficient energy storage systems which are capable of collecting unsteady state energy from sustainable energy resources, i.e., solar, wind, and hydro energy and outputting stable energy supply is of critical importance [1, 2]. Bridging the batteries and the conventional capacitors that deliver high energy density but suffer from relative low power density, high manufacturing cost, and limited life cycles for the former and even though high power density yet too low energy density for the latter, electrochemical capacitors (ECs) offer great advantages of high power capability and exceptional cycle life and reliability [3, 4], ECs possess promising potentials for future applications ranging from portable electronics to hybrid electric vehicles, and to large industrial scale power and energy managements [5]. ECs can be classified into two general categories, electric double layer capacitors (EDLCs) and pseudocapacitors, based on different energy storage principles [6]. In the case of EDLCs, energy storage is achieved via electrostatic accumulation of charges at the electrode material and the electrolyte interfaces. Carbonaceous materials of large specific area, i.e., activated carbons (ACs) [7], carbon nanotubes (CNTs) [8], ordered mesoporous carbons (OMCs) and graphene nanosheets (GNS) [9, 10] are usually utilized as the main component of EDLCs. EDLCs are well known for high power density (>10 KW Kg⁻¹) and long cycle life ($>10^6$ cycles) [11], but

low energy density (<5 Kh/kg) [12, 13] remains the challenge. In contrast to EDLCs, pseudocapacitances arise from electron transfer that follows reduction-oxidation (redox) reactions in the pseudocapacitors [14]. Transition metal oxides including MnO₂ [15], RuO₂ [16], MoO₃ [17], Co₃O₄ [18] and VO_x [19], and electrically conducting polymers (CPs), i.e., poly(aniline) (PANI) [20-22], poly(pyrrole) (PPy) [23-25], and polythiophenes (PThs) [26, 27], have been studied as pseudocapacitive materials. However, the relatively high electrical resistance giving rise to lower power density with respect to transitional metal oxides imposes a limitation for their supercapacitor applications. Conjugated polymers (CPs) have been considered as ideal candidates for electrochemical energy storage owing to high electrical conductivity and coulombic efficiency besides their mechanical versatility, synthetic tailorability, low cost and easy processability [28]. The existing problem regarding CPs is their poor cycling stability from the swelling and shrinking during the cycling redox reactions, which imposes limitations on their applications as electrochemical capacitors [4].

Meanwhile, electrochromic materials that undergo reversible optical changes in the material via the reduction (gain of electrons) or oxidation (loss of electrons) on the passage of an electrical current upon the application of an appropriate potential have gained wide popularity from smart windows for use in cars and buildings, display devices for optical information and storage, and so forth [29, 30]. The electrochromic properties of the conducting

polymers have attracted significant interest both from the academia and industry for their easy processability, rapid response time, high optical contrast, and the ability to modify their structures to create multicolor electrochromes [31].

Among the conductive polymers, polyaniline (PANI) is one of the most studied due to its facile polymerization in aqueous media or nonaqueous media, environmental stability, simple doping/dedoping, high conductivity [32], low cost, high pseudocapacitance [33, 34]. Specially, high pseudocapacitance arising from the versatile redox reactions and corresponding multicolor changes make PANI promising for electrochemical capacitors [35] and electrochromic applications [33]. Another potential application for PANI is their use as giant magnetoresistance sensors. Since the first discovery of giant magnetoresistance (GMR) effect in the thin-film structural metallic materials composed of a pair of ferromagnetic layers (Fe) separated by a non-magnetic metal layer (Cr) in 1988, GMR-based sensors have been designed and widely used in the areas including magnetic data storage (hard disc drive) and biological detection [36]. In the last few decade, carbon-based organic systems are promising materials and have attracted more attentions in the GMR effects since the element carbon has weak spin-orbit coupling and hyperfine interaction. Though the GMR in the organic systems has been obtained at low temperatures, the room temperature GMR signal is still too weak [37] and to obtain large signal at room temperature is still a challenge.

In this talk, the conductive PANI polymer nanocomposites (PNCs) with different nanofillers including tungsten oxide (WO_3), graphite oxide (GO) and silica (SiO_2) nanoparticles were prepared for the applications of the electrochromic devices, electrochemical energy storage and giant magnetoresistance sensors. The morphology, chemical structure, and crystalline structure of the PNCs were studied using atomic force microscopy (AFM), Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR), X-ray diffraction (XRD), and transmission electron microscopy (TEM). Optical and capacitive properties of the composite films for electrochromic (EC) and energy storage devices applications were investigated using spectroelectrochemistry (SEC), cyclic voltammetry (CV) and galvanostatic charge-

discharge measurements. The magnetoresistance property of SiO_2/PANI is also study as well.

2 Materials

Aniline ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_7\text{N}$) was purchased from Sigma Aldrich. Tungsten (VI) ethoxide was obtained from Alfa-Aesar. Silica nanoparticles were obtained from US Research Nanomaterials Inc. Natural graphite powder (SP-1) was provided from Bay Carbon Inc, USA. Indium tin oxide (ITO) glass slides were provided by Fisher and NanoSci Inc. ITO coated glass slides were sonicated in ethanol for 10 min, and then immersed in an aqueous solution containing 4 mL 28.86 wt% ammonium hydroxide, 4 mL 30.0 wt% hydrogen peroxide (both from Fisher) and 20 mL deionized water for 10 min, and sonicated in deionized water for 10 min before usage. Graphite oxide was synthesized following modified Hummers' method [38, 39] using from natural graphite powders as the starting material.

The nanocomposite thin films were fabricated via electropolymerization of aniline monomers onto the GO or WO_3 coated-ITO glass slides which were prepared by spin coating technique. The electropolymerization was performed on an electrochemical working station VersaSTAT 4 potentiostat (Princeton Applied Research). A typical electrochemical cell consisting of Ag/AgCl electrode saturated with KCl serving as the reference electrode, the GO or WO_3 coated-ITO glass slides as the working electrode, and a platinum (Pt) wire as the counter electrode. Silica/PANI composites were prepared by surface initiated polymerization method.

3 Results and Discussion

The interactions between the polymer matrix and the nanoparticles can be verified by the FTIR spectra. Fig.1 shows the FT-TR spectra of (a) WO_3 , (b) PANI, and (c) PANI/ WO_3 nanocomposite films.

PANI and PANI/WO₃ and PANI/GO composite thin film, respectively. The difference in the color switching among the pure PANI and the composite films are inferred to be caused by the interactions between the polymer matrixes and the nanoparticles, as confirmed by the FTIR spectra.

The galvanostatic charge-discharge measurements by chronopotentiometry (CP) were also carried out on the films in 0.5 M H₂SO₄ aqueous solution to evaluate the areal capacitance of the films using the Eq (1) [42]

$$C_s = (2 \times i \times t) / (S \times \Delta V) \quad (3)$$

where C_s is the areal capacitance in F/cm², i is the discharge current in A, t is the discharge time in s, S is active materials surface area of the single electrodes in cm², ΔV is the scanned potential window in V. The areal capacitance of the composite film derived from the discharge in the charge-discharge curve is 0.012 F cm⁻² at a low current density of 0.008 mA cm⁻² and is 0.004 F cm⁻² at a high current density of 0.16 mA cm⁻². WO₃ is found to possess a small poor potential window at those current densities performed on the composite film, and it displays very quick discharge time at higher current density, for example, 6 mA cm⁻².

Fig.2 Charge-discharge curves of PANI/WO₃ hybrid film at different current densities. Reprinted with permission from American Chemical Society.

The areal energy and power density are usually employed for evaluating thin film micro-batteries since the comparison has no dependence on the choice of other components including substrates and

protective packaging [43]. Therefore, areal energy density and power density of the films are plotted using Equation (8) and (9):

$$E = \frac{1}{2} C_s \Delta V^2 \quad (8)$$

$$P = \frac{3600E}{t} \quad (9)$$

where E is the areal energy density in Wh cm⁻², P is the areal power density in W cm⁻². C_s is the specific capacitance in F cm⁻², ΔV is the scanned potential window (excluding IR drop in the beginning of the discharge) in V, t is the discharge time in s. The PANI/GO film can deliver ~2.52 μWh cm⁻² in the low power region of ~0.01 mW cm⁻² and ~0.17 μWh cm⁻² in the high power region of ~0.07 mW cm⁻².

The stability of the capacitors based on conductive polymer films remains as one of most serious issues [44]. The stability of the pure PANI and the composite thin films were studied and compared. Fig. 3 represents the charge density variation with time after different cycles for pure PANI and PANI/WO₃ composite film. No energy storage function existed for the PANI film even after 370 cycles in the charge-discharge cycling. In contrast, the composite thin films exhibit much better stability and the charge density changes little even after 1000 cycles. The chemical bonding formed between the polymer matrix and WO₃ particles is believed to play a vital role in enhancing the stability of the composite films.

Fig. 3 Charge-discharge cycles of (a) the PANI film and (b) PANI/ WO₃ hybrid film in 0.5 M H₂SO₄ aqueous solution. The potential step is 0.8 and -0.2 V holding for 10 s, respectively. Reprinted with permission from American Chemical Society.

Fig.4 Room temperature magnetoresistance of 20 wt% silica/PANI nanocomposites.

Fig. 3 shows the room temperature magnetoresistance (MR) of 20 wt% silica/PANI nanocomposites. It exhibits a positive MR throughout the whole measurement, and the MR value is up to 95.5% in this nonmagnetic nanocomposites. The MR in the hopping system is due to the electron hopping arising from the contraction of the electron wave function and the subsequent reduced average hopping length (R_{hop}) [45].

4 Conclusions

The nanocomposite thin films have been prepared by electrodeposition of PANI onto GO or WO_3 coated-ITO glass. The nanocomposite films display dual-electrochromism and exhibit multiple colors at both positive and negative potentials and energy storage properties.

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